

THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF HEALTHY LIFESTYLE SKILLS IN PRESCHOOL AGE IN A PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION

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Annotation

The article discusses the main directions of developing healthy lifestyle skills among preschoolers in a preschool educational organization

Key words Physical qualities, physical development, sports, preschooler, creativity, form, formation, skill, norm, culture.

The basis for the development of educational programs for preschool education is the educational program “the first step”, which defines the main directions for the development of healthy lifestyle skills in older preschool children. One of the tasks addressed by the standard is the formation of a common culture of children's personality, including the values of a healthy lifestyle, the development of their social, moral, aesthetic, intellectual, physical qualities, initiative, independence and responsibility.

The development of healthy lifestyle skills is reflected in the content of other areas and includes the formation of the foundations of safe behavior in everyday life, society and nature; the formation of independence, purposefulness and self-regulation of one's own actions; the assimilation of norms and values accepted in society; the acquisition of experience in the following types of children's activities: motor, including those related to exercise aimed at the development of physical qualities; contributing to the proper formation of the musculoskeletal system of the body, the development of balance, coordination of movement, large and small motor skills of both hands;

- the formation of initial ideas about some sports, mastering outdoor games with rules;

-the formation of values of a healthy lifestyle, mastering its elementary norms and rules (in nutrition, motor mode, hardening, in the formation of useful habits, etc.);

-formation of primary ideas about oneself and other people.

With regard to healthy lifestyle skills, the targets establish that at the stage of completion of preschool education, the child must have a positive attitude towards the world and people, be mobile, hardy, master the basic movements and be able to manage them. The child should be able to make strong-willed efforts, follow the rules and norms of behavior in various activities, in relationships with people, follow the rules of personal hygiene and safe behavior.

He must have basic knowledge about himself and the world in which he lives, as well as be able to make decisions based on this knowledge and skills.

The basics of developing healthy lifestyle skills in older preschoolers in modern research are considered in several directions.

Most of the research is related to the consideration of the problems of teaching children the basic skills of a healthy lifestyle in the process of physical education.

Thus, the ideas of health-improving physical culture were developed in the theory of formation of healthy lifestyle of preschool children developed by N.V. Sedykh. The scientist believes that "the system-forming factor of the pedagogical system for the formation of the basics of healthy lifestyle is the rational use of technologies for building a functional profile and adaptive biofeedback in the process of physical education."

Biofeedback has long been used for movement training, which is much more successful when a person sees the results of the performed actions when information about the parameters of the performed movements is received. The biofeedback method, or biofeedback, is presented as information about the correctness of performing movements, as well as about the stages of learning healthy lifestyle skills.

According to the researcher, biofeedback-based biofeedback is a fundamentally new approach to teaching older preschool children healthy lifestyle skills, which the author refers to hygiene skills, hardening, proper breathing skills, the basics of self-massage, motor activity. At the same time, physical education is the main factor of a healthy lifestyle.

In the same direction, O.V. Morozova conducts her research, in whose works the scientific and theoretical substantiation of the methodology for the formation of basic healthy lifestyle skills in preschool children using the biofeedback method is presented. This technique helps to create motivation for children to exercise and develop self-esteem and self-regulation skills.

The object of research in O.S. Schneider's dissertation is teaching healthy lifestyle to preschoolers in the system of physical culture and recreation activities of an educational institution. The paper substantiates the methodology of teaching preschool children healthy lifestyle skills in regular physical activity, which allows them to develop conscious skills and the need to maintain health.

One of the directions of developing a healthy lifestyle among preschoolers is the influence of social conditions on health.

The activity of the child, his independent actions, according to N.G. Bykova, is associated with the interaction of the individual with the environment. The microenvironment of a child in senior preschool age consists of a family, a team of a preschool educational organization, a group that he attends, various communities of people in which children are united by a community of interests, where the child acquires life experience. Consequently, according to the researcher, the most effective skills of a healthy lifestyle in older preschool children will be developed in the activities of a preschool educational organization of an "open type", i.e. one that uses the potential of various societies that influence the increase in social contacts and the success of the formation of healthy lifestyle skills. The activities of all services of a preschool educational organization should be aimed at creating conditions for the development of healthy lifestyle skills among older preschoolers, however, the priority is the work of a preschool educational organization with the family.

The decisive role of the family in introducing a child to a healthy lifestyle is pointed out by many authors (L.G. Kasyanova, S.Y. Tolstova, T.E. Sergienko, N.A. Andreeva, E.V. Vodneva).

L.G. Kasyanova notes that the complex process of introducing preschoolers to a healthy lifestyle is influenced by public opinion, educational technology, the personalities of teachers, the state and orientation of family education. The latter is an integral part of a unified system for the formation of a conscious attitude to a healthy lifestyle in

preschool children and "no matter how complete and deep it may be within the framework of a preschool institution, it will never become complete without the help of parents, without their active participation in this process."

The conclusions made in T.E. Sergienko's dissertation make it possible to create a modern system of interaction between teachers and parents in the field of healthy lifestyle formation for preschoolers. The interaction of teachers and parents in the system created by the author is carried out from the standpoint of cooperation and dialogue, the social request of parents is taken into account in

the planning of the work of an educational institution, forms of work with the family are used that increase its activity.

One of the objectives of E.V. Vodneva's research was to develop the content of pedagogical education for parents of older preschool children in valeological issues of education. The scientists have developed recommendations for parents of older preschoolers on educating children about the value of health and the development of healthy lifestyle skills.

Andreeva N.A. designed the technology of interaction between a preschool educational organization and a family for the formation of a healthy lifestyle in older preschool children. The researcher theoretically justified and tested in practice the pedagogical conditions for the implementation of this technology. She attributed to them the reorientation of parents and teachers to a healthy lifestyle, replenishment of theoretical knowledge, mastery of wellness systems in the field of physical culture, the development of adequate ideas about their bodies in children, the formation of the need for a healthy lifestyle, the development of basic skills of prevention and hygiene. The interaction of the preschool and the family is ensured by the active inclusion of all participants in the educational process in the formation of the foundations of a healthy lifestyle.

S.Y. Tolstova points out the factors of the family environment that determine the high incidence of diseases in children: incomplete family composition, poor maternal health, low financial security, unfavorable microclimate in the family, frequent conflict situations, bad habits of parents, irrational nutrition. The researcher adheres to the point of view that a healthy lifestyle of a child is largely due to the participation and example of parents, who play a leading role in developing a stereotype of a "healthy lifestyle" in children. In this regard, she reveals the idea of educating parents on the formation of a healthy lifestyle.

Another direction in the development of healthy lifestyle skills in preschoolers is related to the impact of the surrounding nature and environmental conditions on human health and lifestyle.

As Z.I. Tyumaseva notes, environmental education and education are a fundamental component of the formation of a healthy lifestyle, since the relationship between man and nature is a criterion of human health.

According to L. Sudakova, the ability to communicate with nature in practical everyday life is a direct way to preserve and strengthen health. The author writes that the more nature occupies a place in a child's life, the easier and more effectively healthy lifestyle skills are formed in preschool childhood.

Considering the ecological aspect of the problem of developing healthy lifestyle skills in preschoolers, T.V. Kamenskaya identifies the concept of "environmental health" as a qualitative characteristic that determines the possibility of maintaining human health at a high level. One of the conceptual provisions of the pedagogical system model created by her is the greening of the kindergarten educational environment.

O.N. Lazareva argues that it is necessary to ensure the transfer of mandatory social guidelines into the child's inner plan; knowledge, skills, values and ideals, principles and rules of society's attitude to the environment. Selecting values in the content of environmental education, the scientist focuses on such concepts as "health" and "healthy lifestyle".

A comprehensive program of ecological and valeological education for older preschool children is presented in the dissertation study by E.G. Kushnina. The phrase "ecological-valeological", according to the author of the program, reflects not just the fact of combining ecological and valeological knowledge, but the deep interconnection and interdependence of these types of education. The pedagogical conditions for the effective development of healthy lifestyle skills are a health-saving environment in a preschool educational organization and cultural educational technology.

L.T. Kuznetsova includes the development of healthy lifestyle skills in the content of the health-saving competence of older preschool children, along with environmental, valeological knowledge, motives that have an ecological and conservation orientation towards themselves and the world around them, encouraging them to lead a healthy lifestyle, as well as a value attitude to their health. The researcher has developed a model of the process of developing the health-saving competence of older preschoolers, in which the child's skills and abilities to act in various life situations without harming his health are considered as a result of education. The objectives of the program, which represents a meaningful block of the model, include the following: to form behavior and experience of maintaining health in any life situations; to develop skills in personal hygiene, nutrition culture, providing basic medical self-help and assistance; to introduce physical culture values.

The central core of the pedagogical technology of forming children's ideas about a healthy lifestyle, developed by L.G. Kasyanova, is also an integrated approach to the selection and development of the content of the material offered to children, to the forms and methods of its presentation.

The development of healthy lifestyle skills in older preschool children, according to the author, contributes to children's awareness of the dependence of health on lifestyle and the state of the surrounding environment and the influence of the surrounding social and ecological environment on a healthy lifestyle. There are different points of view among researchers on the problem of introducing healthy lifestyle skills training into the educational process of a modern preschool institution, which is already overloaded.

Thus, Z.I. Tyumaseva draws attention to the optimal education system, which should be as close as possible to the child's life environment, the traditions of his people, the environment of formal and informal education and upbringing.

Among the possible forms of work for the development of healthy lifestyle skills in preschoolers, S.B. Sharmanova recommends using classes of the cognitive cycle "Health lessons", thematic physical education classes, entertainment and holidays, "Health Days" with a valeological orientation.

Most researchers, along with the educational form of developing healthy lifestyle skills (a course of special classes), suggest using other forms of work with preschoolers: excursions, physical education and recreation activities, preventive and hardening procedures, games.

The researcher uses game technologies (educational, educational, developmental, cognitive, productive, socializing, creative, communicative, didaktik, story-role, mobile, labor, folk games) as mechanisms for developing healthy lifestyle skills.

The researcher considers such methodological forms of developing healthy lifestyle skills of preschoolers by means of game technologies as: sports clubs, sections, sports holidays, healthy lifestyle week, quizzes, games, contests, children's sports weeks, attendance and participation in various events aimed at forming a healthy lifestyle, etc.

Thus, the analysis of scientific The literature on the problem of developing healthy lifestyle skills in preschoolers allows us to draw the following conclusions.

Researchers agree that older preschool children need to be given knowledge about ways to preserve and strengthen their health, teach appropriate techniques and foster a value attitude towards a healthy lifestyle. Therefore, the concept of "healthy lifestyle skills of preschoolers" covers the children's knowledge and ideas about

ways to preserve health; understanding the importance of a healthy lifestyle, focusing on it; the desire and ability to independently use health preservation techniques in everyday life.

The main directions of developing healthy lifestyle skills in preschoolers are: the development of healthy lifestyle skills in the process of physical education.

Among the possible forms of work to develop healthy lifestyle skills in preschoolers in a preschool educational organization, researchers name physical education, environmental, valeological classes; integrated classes; excursions, physical education and recreation activities, preventive and tempering procedures, various games, conversations, quizzes, healthy lifestyle weeks, sports holidays.

Literature:

1. Djalalova, N. (2023). BO 'LAJAK MUSIQA O 'QITUVCHISINING KREATIVLIK JIHATLARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(4), 162-167.
2. Xusanovna, D. N. (2023). YOSHLARNING ESTETIK TAFAKKURINI YUKSALTIRISHDA MUSIQA MADANIYATIDAGI MA'NAVIY ASPEKTLAR. *FINLAND" MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS"*, 14(1).
3. Djalalova, Nigora Xusanovna (2024). YOSHLARNING ESTETIK TAFAKKURINI YUKSALISHIDA MUSIQA MADANIYATIDAGI KONSEPSIYALAR. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 4 (2), 234-241.
4. ugli Abdullaev, S. S. (2021). Social Involvement in Students Results of Experimental Work on the Development of Virtues. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(7), 42-47.
5. Sobirjon, A. (2023). Affection as a Person's Ideological Immunity. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 4(6), 29-33.
6. Sidikova, S. G. (2023). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI JISMONIY RIVOJLANTIRISH VA ULARDA SOG 'LOM TURMUSH TARZINI SHAKLLANTIRISH-IJTIMOIIY-PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. *Conferencea*, 34-43.
7. Sidikova, S. G., & Mohidil, M. (2023). HARDENING AS THE BASIS OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. *Conferencea*, 119-134.
8. Sabirovna, S. G., & Temurovna, Y. Z. (2023, December). OPPORTUNITIES FOR EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETENCIES IN THE FIELD OF "PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT AND THE FORMATION OF A

HEALTHY LIFESTYLE" OF CHILDREN OF EARLY AND PRESCHOOL AGE. In E Conference Zone (pp. 63-71).

9. Ashurova, A. O. (2023). PROBLEMS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ECOLOGICAL CULTURE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS. American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research, 12, 113-118.

10. Ашурова, О. (2022). ЭКОЭСТЕТИК МАДАНИЯТНИ БЎЛАЖАК МАКТАБГАЧА ТАЪЛИМ МУТАХАССИСЛАРИДА РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ МАЗМУНИ ВА АСОСИЙ БОСҚИЧЛАРИ. Теория и практика современной науки, (4 (82)), 13-16.

11. АШУРОВА, О. ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ. ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ Учредители: ООО" Институт управления и социально-экономического развития", (4), 13-16.

12. Mamasoli, S. S., & Mirzodajonovich, S. M. (2022). THE ROLE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS IN THE INTELLECTUAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS. Scientific Impulse, 1(3), 1136-1142.

13. Mamasoliyevich, S. S. (2022). USING INTERACTIVE TECHNIQUES IN THE CLASSROOM PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS (USING FOOTBALL LESSONS AS AN EXAMPLE). Scientific Impulse, 1(3), 1118-1123.

14. Mamasoliyevich, S. S., & Marubjanovich, S. N. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF ENDURANCE OF TEENAGERS IN SPORTS SCHOOLS IN ATHLETICS. Conferencea, 109-125.

15. Sidikov, M. S., & Marubjanovich, N. S. (2023). EDUCATION OF THE ENDURANCE OF TEENAGERS ENGAGED IN ATHLETICS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF SECTIONS. Open Access Repository, 4(02), 27-37.

16. Mamajonovich, M. N. (2023). ASSESSMENT OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT TRAINING OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. Conferencea, 23-36.

17. Sidikov, M. S. (2023). USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TEHNOLOGIES IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSONS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF FOOTBALL LESSONS). American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research, 9, 63-71.

18. Mamasoliyevich, S. S. (2023). AGE-SPECIFIC CHANGES IN THE INDICATORS OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. Conferencea, 298-310.

19. Mamasoli, S. S., & Marubjanovich, N. S. (2022). " EDUCATION OF ENDURANCE OF YOUTH ENGAGED IN ATHLETICS. Scientific Impulse, 1(3), 1118-1125.

